

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20062253

A REVIEW ON THE IMPACT OF SPIRITUAL QUOTIENT AND EMOTIONAL QUOTIENT ON BURNOUT AND JOB SATISFACTION AMONGST IT PROFESSIONALS

Soumya S Nair^{1*}, Dr Rejoice Thomas²

¹Research Scholar Christ (Deemed to be University), Bengaluru
Email: soumyanairmccblr@gmail.com, ORCID iD: 0000-0003-3801-286X

²Associate Professor Christ (Deemed to be University), Bengaluru
Email: rejoice.thomas@christuniversity.in, ORCID iD: 0000-0002-8701-6720

Received: 02/12/2025

Accepted: 28/03/2026

Corresponding Author: Soumya S Nair
(soumyanairmccblr@gmail.com)

ABSTRACT

Researchers have attempted to understand how Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence affect IT employees and their performance and how it aids IT companies while increasing job satisfaction on the basis of existing literature. The purpose of this research is to analyse the Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of IT employees and discover their contribution towards their burnout and job satisfaction. This study intends to examine the extent of the impact of SQ and EQ on Burnout and job satisfaction among IT professionals and provide suggestions that can incorporate spirituality and Emotional Quotient in a positive way at the workplace. Job Satisfaction has undergone drastic redefinition and is the result of key factors which were otherwise ignored. The degree of Burnout of the employees was also identified as a significant aspect that can affect the productivity of the workforce in various analyses. Further, the role of two components of Organisation Behaviour, viz, Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence on the above factors have also been analysed many times. Recent research indicates that people's EQ and SQ might be the reason for success than their I.Q. This study reviewed the previous research which explored the association between EI, SI, Burnout and Job Satisfaction among employees with special reference to IT Sector. The findings of this study are EQ and SQ are the factors responsible for decreasing the level of Burnout and better Job Satisfaction and have a positive impact on Individual as well as Organisational Performance. The aim of this study is to provide a critical review of the literature on Spiritual Quotient and Emotional Quotient among IT professionals and their impact on Burnout and Job Satisfaction.

KEYWORDS: Burnout, IT Professionals, Emotional Quotient (EQ), Job Satisfaction, Spiritual Quotient (SQ).

INTRODUCTION

IT Professionals constitute a significant number of employed professionals in India. They have an immense contribution to the Gross Domestic Product of the Country. There are various factors that contribute to their performance. Spiritual Intelligence is one such factor that can have an impact on Job satisfaction and Burnout among IT Professionals.

SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE

As defined by Wigglesworth as, **SQ** is the ability to do things with wisdom and compassion and maintain inner and outer peace regardless of the situation.

Spiritual intelligence is the ability of an individual to access higher meanings, values, abiding purposes, and unconscious aspects of the self and to embed these meanings, values, and purposes in living richer and more creative lives. People with a high level of SI will lead a healthier, happier, and more productive lives at their workplace.

Spirituality is considered one of the key factors for the success of employees and ultimately for their professional life. gave three components of spiritual intelligence: - the ability to create meaning based on a deep understanding of existing questions, the ability to use multiple levels of consciousness in problem-solving and the awareness of the interconnection of all beings to each other and to the transcendent.

Danah Zohar has given the following Principles underlying Spiritual Quotient

1. Self-awareness
2. Spontaneity
3. Being vision
4. Holism
5. Compassion
6. Celebration of Diversity
7. Field independence
8. Humility
9. Tendency to ask fundamental
10. Ability to reframe
11. Positive use of adversity
12. Sense of vocation. (wikipedia.org, n.d.)

(bernard, 2008) has given the below Dimensions as

- Divinity,
 - Mindfulness,
 - Extrasensory perception,
 - Community, Intellectuality,
 - Trauma,
 - Childhood spirituality
- Spiritual Intelligence is something that can reflect

a person's behaviour and attitude. Hence there is a room for investigation as to whether it effects the performance and job satisfaction of an employee. This study throws lights on this enquiry.

Emotional intelligence (EQ) is the ability to recognize, understand, and regulate our emotions and to respond to those emotions in constructive ways that allow us to communicate,

empathize with others and overcome challenges. It is the ability to regulate our emotions according to the existing situations.

In other words, it is the ability to manage our emotions before our emotions manage us. The

five components of EQ are

1. Self -Awareness-The ability to recognize and understand our own emotions.
2. Self -Regulation-The ability to regulate and manage our emotions.
3. Social Skills-The ability to interact well with others.
4. Empathy-The ability to understand how others are feeling.
5. Motivation-The ability to get motivated through internal rewards and not just from material benefits.

Emotional Management comprises of managing our emotions according to the situations

existing in our surrounding. It involves the strategic analysis of the existing conditions and

making your emotions adapt to the same. It is relevant for the workforce to have an effective Emotional Management process to be successfully productive and efficient in their respective job profiles. The proper realisation of all the five components of EQ can facilitate a better Emotional Management. It can be improved and may influence professional success than IQ.

Burnout and Job Satisfaction are two important outcomes of the differences in the SI and EI among the employees.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- To examine whether there is an impact of SQ and EQ on job satisfaction among IT Professionals.
- To determine the impact of SQ and EQ on Burnout among IT Professionals.
- To convey the relevance of incorporating spirituality and EQ positively to IT Professionals in their workplace.
- To examine the relationship between EQ and SQ based on earlier studies conducted on the above topic.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Though many have been conducted to assess the SQ and EQ and their impact, a need was felt to learn

its impact on burnout and Job satisfaction of IT Professionals. The conclusion of this study could lead to a better understanding of SQ and EQ amongst IT professionals and how it can affect their burnout and job satisfaction. The results could ideally help employers to change certain work policies, and employees to understand what the level of their SI and EI is and how can they reduce their level of burnout and thereby increase job satisfaction. Suggestions could be provided to them based on the results.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

All the previous relevant studies conducted on EQ and SQ are categorised into five sections.

SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE

All four components of SQ have a relationship with the work-life balance of working IT professionals. Spirituality is an essential indicator of work-life balance, and SQ leads to higher rates of work management and personal life among employees in this sector. Accordingly, it is applied in policy planning and further research in human resource management in various organizations (pandey).

The consistent existence of SQ at the workplace can enhance the employees' job satisfaction, which eventually leads to the reduction of workplace deviant behaviour (WDB). The study points to the importance of workplace spirituality for employees as it can reduce the WDB (Wohyano). Workplace spirituality, designation and gender are found to be related to workplace spirituality (Ujjal, 2018), (bernard, 2008) has determined that EQ impacts the job satisfaction and turnover intentions of employees. SQ had an impact on job satisfaction positively but had a negative impact on the turnover intention of employees in mobile telecommunication companies. There is a positive and significant relationship between spiritual intelligence dimensions and personality traits but no significant correlation between personal meaning production and transcendental awareness dimensions and neuroticism personality traits (Ahmad, 2015) Humans should develop their SQ, living the highest quality of life (QoL) (Sharma R. k.) Spiritual Intelligence enhances the ability of individuals to appreciate others in a better way.. Spiritually intelligent people are said to have the capacity to solve problems more systematically. They are very conscious and always come up with great ideas.

(Vaughan, 2000) has given three components of spiritual intelligence: - the ability to create meaning

with a deep understanding of existing questions, the ability to use multiple levels of consciousness in problem-solving, an awareness of the interconnection of all beings to each other. The major factor associated with schoolteachers' decision to leave or to remain in the teaching profession is their job satisfaction, Job satisfaction is related to working conditions and level of professionalism is a key factor in successfully recruiting and retaining teachers (Stimmerman, 2000). Job Satisfaction is "a pleasurable emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job and an attitude toward one's job (Jafri, 2000). Teacher's job satisfaction refers to a teacher's affective relation to his or her teaching role and is the function of the perceived relationship between what one wants from teaching and what one perceives it is offering to a teacher (Papanastasiou, 2009). Spiritual intelligence provides a sense of personal wholeness, goal and direction, He pointed out teachers with high level of spiritual Intelligence are able to mould students from all age groups to experience a wholesome life filled with self-respect and creativity (Dincer, 2009). Teachers with high levels of SI have maximum satisfaction with their jobs. Spiritual Intelligence has positive influence on Job Satisfaction (Cherati, 2013)

An organization can conduct itself fairly in a cooperative and responsible manner with a vision to foster charity and creativeness leading to higher productivity and accomplishment which can further supplement self-esteem of the employees so that they get the sense of job satisfaction.

The most important functions of spiritual intelligence in the workplace are to: -provide peace of mind, create mutual understanding and rapport between colleagues, increase job satisfaction and reduce job stress.

Spiritual intelligence training plays a crucial role on decreasing the levels of such psychological disorders as interpersonal sensitivity, somatization, obsessive-compulsive disorder, depression, anxiety, aggression, phobic, paranoid ideation, and psychoticism in the experimental group. (Aydın Söylemez, 2019)

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

Individuals who can regulate their emotions have high levels of EQ as they correctly perceive and appraise their emotional states, wwwwww and when to express their feelings, and control their state of mind. '. This set of characteristics, deals with the perception. There exists a relationship between EI and physical as well as psychological health (P Salovey, 1999). There is a relationship between EI,

stress and a number of measures of psychological health, such as depression, hopelessness and suicidal ideation among young people. (Joseph Ciarrochi, 2002). Stress was associated with greater, reported depression, hopelessness and suicidal ideation among people high in emotional perception (EP) and greater suicidal ideation among those low in managing others' emotions (MOE).

The humour skills programmes improve emotional well-being by increasing self-efficacy, positive thinking, optimism and perceptions of control while decreasing negative thinking, perceptions of stress, depression, anxiety and stress. (Shelly.A.Crowford, 2011). EI and job burnout were explained in terms of mental health variance of physical health. (Mohammad Ali Mohammadyfar, 2009)

EI and its various component abilities are associated with better health outcomes. It is also dealing with lower levels of stress. Two components of EI, namely, the ability to appraise and express emotions and the ability to utilize emotions significantly moderated the stress health relationship. The ability to appraise and express emotions affected an individual's health; It is a positive resource in high-stress conditions. (Anil Kumar Choubey, 2009)

Emotional intelligence plays a moderating role in the experience of job stress. (Leila Karimi, 2013)

(Hifza Mubeen, 2016) stated that organizational learning significantly and partially mediates the relationship between EQ and performance as well as knowledge management and organizational performance. So, emotional intelligence and knowledge are important inputs that improve the performance and results of any organization

BURNOUT

Burnout is a response to chronic emotional and interpersonal stressors on the job. (Christina Maslach, 2001).

A negative relationship was established between one dimension of burnout, emotional exhaustion, and subsequent work performance. (Thomas A Wright, 1988)

(M, 2011) concludes that an understanding of the interaction between an employee and his or her environment is critical to ascertain the reason for burnout.

(Chernis, 1992) states that subjects who were more burned-out early in their careers were less likely to change careers and more flexible in their approach to work as rated by confidants at the time of follow-up. The results suggest that early career burnout does not

seem to lead to any significant, negative, long-term consequences. However, burnout occurring later in the career might have more serious long-term effects.

JOB SATISFACTION

Job satisfaction is a worker's sense of achievement and success on the job and the amount of Job content. It is directly linked to productivity as well as to a healthy personal life. Job satisfaction means doing a that you enjoy, doing it in the best way and being rewarded for one's efforts. It means enthusiasm and happiness with one's work. It leads to recognition, income, promotion, and the achievement of other goals that lead to a feeling of fulfilment. (Kaliski, 2007)

When the employees feel that they are good contributors it will encourage them to involve and participate more for the sake of the organization. Regarding this dimension, when manager communicates effectively with the employees, listens to their complaints, answering their questions and provide for them ways to communicate effectively, the organization will encourage them to enhance their work and feel satisfied about their jobs. (Suliman Ibraheem Shelash Al-Hawary, 2013)

Job satisfaction is the collection of feeling and beliefs that people have about their current job. People's levels of degrees of job satisfaction can range from extreme satisfaction to extreme dissatisfaction. In addition to having attitudes about their jobs as a whole. People also can have attitudes about various aspects of their jobs such as the kind of work they do, their co-workers, supervisors or subordinates and their pay. (George, 2008)

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE, SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE, BURNOUT AND JOB SATISFACTION

'EQ' is the ability identify one's own and other's feelings and emotions, to differentiate among them and to use this result to assist in one's thoughts and activities. 'SQ' is the true feeling of being attached to one's inner self, others, and the entire universe.

Several studies have indicated that there is a relationship between Spiritual Intelligence, Burnout and Job Satisfaction. This relationship depends upon how positively the Spirituality is understood and implemented in the workplace for reducing burnout and stress and enhancing Job Satisfaction.

Emotional Intelligence positively influences the job satisfaction and turnover intentions of employees. Spiritual Intelligence was found to influence job satisfaction positively but had a negative impact on the turnover intention of

employees in mobile telecommunication companies. (Benard Korankye, 2021)

There is no direct relationship between organizational commitment and spiritual intelligence. There is an indirect relationship occurs among organizational commitment and spiritual intelligence that is media by with job satisfaction. (Mustabsar Awais, 2015)

SQ leads to higher rates of managing work and personal life among employees and hence it can be used in policy planning and further research in human resource management in organizations. (Singh, 2021)

Emotional and Spiritual Intelligence plays a crucial role in building creativity and innovation among the entrepreneurs. SQ motivates an entrepreneur that makes them stand out from the others. (Susan Tee Suan, 2012)

An individual who has a good combination (of SI and EI) could produce a balanced generation to have a strong self defence to face life challenges. It clears spiritual and emotional level of intelligence significantly influences an individual 's level of achievement. The stability in both (SI and EI) elements is not only better for good achievements but also develop a positive attitude of students. High level of SI will also help students to control their laziness and avoid all other emotional disturbances which could lead negative impacts on their level of achievement. Therefore, SI is much more related with EI, these are inseparable. (Sodhi, 2016)

The above model describes four core intelligences. It shows a pyramid to demonstrate the simplest sequence of development. This is a very simple model which is helpful to imagine relation between development of child and development of intelligence. (Wigglesworth, p. 2006)

There is a relationship between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction among teachers of vocational and technical colleges in the Southern Zone, Malaysia. There is a relevant positive relationship between the respondent's emotional intelligence and job satisfaction. EQ varied according to the work experience. There was no difference in the level of emotional intelligence in terms of gender and age. (Mohamad Zaid Mustafa, 2014)

There exists a relationship between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction among bank employees in the Greek banking sector. EQ and job satisfaction was studied and described the impact of emotional intelligence on demographic variables such as gender of employees, age, educational level, and their previous experience in the Greek banking sector. Gender, age, marital status, and job position

affects the level of emotional intelligence of employees in the banking sector. Additionally, it influences the everyday life of employees and modulates the level of professional satisfaction. (Siati, 2014)

Emotion has an important role in generating job satisfaction. They stated that employees with higher emotional EQ in comparison with those with lower EI can adjust their special effects and it leads to more job satisfaction. Also, EQ can lead to a pleasant work environment and influence employees 'job satisfaction and effective management. (Fasihizadeh & Nouri, 2012)

(Ghani, 2013) conducted a study among the employees of banking organizations working at managerial and non-managerial levels to explore the influence of emotional intelligence in reducing occupational stress. The mediating effect of emotional intelligence on job satisfaction and job stress was also realised. Jammu and Kashmir was selected for the purpose of the study. The study concluded stating that stress and EI exist among employees.

And EQ works as a mediating variable. The stress process increases the level of job satisfaction in employees by decreasing the level of job dissatisfaction.

(Gholami, 2013) researched to ascertain the relationship between emotional intelligence, job satisfaction and organizational commitment of personnel in banks and financial institutions of Darrehshahr City. The conclusion was no meaningful relationship between emotional intelligence and organizational commitment but it was seen between organizational commitment and job satisfaction. Study also revealed that individuals' emotional intelligence had no impact on their job satisfaction.

(Akhthar, 2012) Emotional intelligence and job satisfaction is positively correlated. He suggested that teachers should be capable of managing their' and others "emotions to have a positive influence on themselves as well on others.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This is an exploratory study which is conducted with the help of secondary data. The data has been collected from various sources: such as books, journals, and websites etc. Sample size is 40 articles, from the period 1988-2021. The variables are Emotional Quotient, Spiritual Quotient, Burnout and Job Satisfaction.

OBSERVATIONS AND FINDINGS

After the review of literature, we can find an obvious relationship between EQ and SQ with

Burnout and Job Satisfaction. They are interlinked to each other and have an inverse relationship with each other. The study indicated that employees are satisfied at their work, and it is substantially influenced by their Spiritual Intelligence. Decreased level of SI and EI has resulted in higher levels of burnout and decreased job satisfaction. Higher levels of EI is sufficient to allow employees to contribute more effectively to changes in the organization. EI followed by SI increases an individual's capability to take up more responsibility in decision-making. EI and SI in the workplace can assist in better adjustment and increase the productivity and performance of each individual and organization.

Future study in this area might convey that IT professionals with high spiritual quotient perform well and contribute more resulting in an increase in individual productivity and the overall performance of the company.

In the current scenario, it is essential to integrate both SI and EI to attain maximum employee performance. Increasing the levels of EI and SI can help the organisations as employees will be able to contribute more efficiently and adapt to the changes more effectively. It will psychologically enable the employees to take up their responsibilities more diligently. As a whole Improvement in SI and EI can contribute towards the development of each individual employee as well as the organisation.

CONCLUSION

People often like to view a meaning and value in their life and work as well as to make a difference to the life of others. Spiritual Intelligence is the main reason that results to maximum level of intelligence without any religious bias and aids to analyse self in a better form. Sogyal Rinpoche says in the Tibetan book of living and Dying that True spirituality means

REFERENCES

- Ahmad, N. (2015). The relationship between spiritual intelligence and personality traits among Jordanian university students.
- Akhthar, N. (2012).
- Anil Kumar Choubey, S. K. (2009). Role of Emotional Intelligence in Stress and Health. *Indian Journal Social Science Researches*, 122-134.
- Aydın Söylemez, M. K. (2019). Studying Spiritual Intelligence As a Predictor on. *SPIRITUAL PSYCHOLOGY AND COUNSELING*, 109-122.
- Benard Korankye, E. A. (2021). Exploring the Impact of Emotional and Spiritual Intelligence on Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intention. *SEISENCE JOURNAL OF MANAGEMENT*.
- bernard, E. (2008). Exploring the Impact of Emotional and Spiritual Intelligence on Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intention: Evidence from Mobile Telecommunication Companies in Ghana. *SEISENCE Journal of Management*, 31-46.
- C Maslach, ,. (2016). *Burnout*.
- Cherati, M. &. (2013). The mediating role of job satisfaction between spiritual intelligence and organizational

understanding that if we are interdependent with everything and everyone, even least important thought, word and action has real outcomes throughout the universe. So, IT Professionals as contributors for the economic development of the nation should understand their deeper nature and their conscious development. Hence the significance of Spiritual Intelligence. It impacts the burnout and job satisfaction level of IT employees. So, efforts could be made to enhance the circumstances and factors that could possibly enable them to enhance their Spirituality in a positive manner.

EI and SI are very much important for individual to be dynamic at their workplace. SO it is highly recommended that all the sectors of society and employers in particular should encourage, motivate and enable scenarios to development the same as EI and SI are real contributors of the development an individual's careers and increase their probability of adapting to changed and demanding business situations.

IMPLICATIONS

- **IT PROFESSIONALS**-IT professionals will be able to analyse their level of SI and EI. They can assess what are the situations wherein their level of SI and EI decreases and how it impacts their level of Burnout and Job Satisfaction.
- **IT COMPANIES**- The companies will be able to identify the situations during which the level of SI and EI of employees tend to decrease which can affect their Job Satisfaction and Burnout which can have an impact on their overall performance. They can subsequently make sufficient changes in the work policies.
- **HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGER**-The results could ideally aid HR managers of IT companies to modify existing HR policies considering the level of their SI and EI.

- commitment. *Journal of Research*.
- Chernis, C. (1992). Long-term consequences of burnout: An exploratory study. *Journal of Organisation Behaviour*.
- Christina Maslach, W. B. (2001). JOB BURNOUT. *ANNUAL REVIEW OF PSYCHOLOGY*, 397-422.
- Dincer. (2009).
- emmon. (2000).
- EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND JOB STRESS AMONG BANK EMPLOYEES. (2013).
- Fasihizadeh, O. &, & Nouri. (2012).
- George. (2008). Job satisfaction among urban secondary-school teachers in Namibia.
- Ghani. (2013). EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND JOB STRESS AMONG BANK EMPLOYEES.
- Gholami. (2013).
- Hanefer. (2016).
- Hifza Mubeen, H. A. (2016). Impact of emotional intelligence and knowledge management on organizational performance: mediating role of organizational learning. *ournal of Management Info (JMI)*, 12-17.
- Jafri, S. &. (2000). Organizational Satisfaction in the 21st-Century Internal Audit Function: Trends That Impact Internal Audit Departments.
- Joseph Ciarrochi, F. p. (2002). Emotional intelligence moderates the relationship between stress and mental health. 197-209.
- Kaliski. (2007).
- Leila Karimi, S. G. (2013). Emotional rescue: the role of emotional intelligence and emotional labour on well-being and job-stress among community nurses. 176-186.
- M, J. (2011). Job Burnout. *Journal of Employment COunselling*.
- Mohamad Zaid Mustafa, F. N. (2014). Emotional Intelligence and Organizational Commitment among-Polytechnic Lecturers: A Case Study On Malaysia Northern Zone.
- Mohammad Ali Mohammadyfar, M. S. (2009). The Effect of Emotional Intelligence and Job Burnout on. *Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psycholo*, 219-226.
- Mustabsar Awais, M. S. (2015). A Review: The Job Satisfaction Act as Mediator between Spiritual Intelligence and Organizational Commitment.
- P Salovey, B. (1999). *Coping -The Pscychology of what works*.
- pandey, T. (n.d.). The impact of Spiritual Intelligence on work life balance of service sector employees.
- Papanastasiou, Z. &. (2009).
- Ramachandran. (2017).
- Sharma. (2017).
- Sharma, R. k. (n.d.). FROM INTELLIGENCE TOWARDS SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE. *Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies*,.
- Shelly.A.Crowford, N. (2011). Promoting emotional well-being through the use of humour. *The Journal of Positive Pschychology*.
- Siati, M. (2014). Emotional Intelligence and Job Satisfaction in Greek Banking Sector. *Research in Applied Economics*, 225-239.
- Singh, S. (2021). THE IMPACT OF SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE ON WORK-LIFE BALANCE OF SERVICE SECTOR EMPLOYEES . *International Journal of Modern Agriculture*, 509-520.
- Sisk. (2008). *Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies*
- Sodhi, R. (2016). Emotional Intelligence and Spirituality: A Review. *The INternational Journal Of Indian Psychology*.
- Stimmerman, S. a. (2000).
- Sulieman Ibraheem Shelash Al-Hawary, K. A.-Q.-Z. (2013). THE IMPACT OF INTERNAL MARKETING ON EMPLOYEE'S JOB SATISFACTION OF COMMERCIAL BANKS IN JORDAN,. *NTERDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY RESEARCH IN BUSINESS*.
- Susan Tee Suan, K. R. (2012). Relationship Between Emotional Intelligence And Spiritual. *International Conference on Asia Pacific Business Innovation and*, 261-267.
- Thomas A Wright, D. G. (1988). The contribution of burnout to work performance. *Journal of Organisation Behaviour*, 491-499.
- Ujjal. (2018). Influence of Workplace Spirituality on Job SatisfactionA study among employees working in IT industry in India.

Vaughan. (2000).

Wigglesworth, C. (n.d.). Why Spiritual Intelligence Is Essential to Mature Leadership.

wikipedia.org. (n.d.). Retrieved from wikipedia.org.

Wohyano, A. (n.d.). The influence of spiritual leadership on spirituality, conscientiousness and job satisfaction and its impact on the reduction of workplace deviant behaviour.